

fall and flooding at critical crop growth stages in 1997-98. In both good and bad years, the SPAD-guided N treatment recorded a significantly higher grain yield than the control, but it was on a par with the local N recommendation in all three cropping seasons. The AEN values of the SPAD treatment were 1.5–2.5 times that of the local N recommendation (Table 1). Savings in fertilizer rates of 50–65 kg N ha⁻¹ were recorded during the DS; 78–95 kg N ha⁻¹ were saved during the WS. Data also indicated that no basal N application is required for the SPAD method in soils of the new Cauvery Delta because there was no substantial increase in grain yield with a basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹.

In farms of the old Cauvery Delta, the crop response to different N

treatments was similar to that observed in the new Cauvery Delta (Table 2). Likewise, AEN values followed the same trend. Grain yield was highest for the SPAD method, but it was on a par with the local N recommendation and SPAD method with a basal application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹. The data again indicated that basal N application is not advantageous for various soil types in the old Cauvery Delta. An average savings of 80 kg ha⁻¹ for N fertilizer was obtained in both the DS and WS.

These results clearly demonstrated the advantage of using the chlorophyll meter technique to fine-tune N recommendations for various seasons in the Cauvery Delta. There is a potential to save 50–95 kg N ha⁻¹ if refined N recommendations are used. This study focused on using a

single SPAD threshold value to assess N needs of rice crops. Further research is ongoing to determine the effect of using a range of SPAD values (e.g., 32–34, 35–37, 38–40, etc.) for synchronizing N application with crop demand in rice.

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Efficiency of controlled-release urea and coated urea fertilizers in irrigated transplanted rice in Andhra Pradesh, India

K. Padmaja, R.M. Kumar, S.P. Singh, A.G.K. Murthy, and S.V. Subbaiah, Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad 500030, Andhra Pradesh, India

Nitrogen (N) is one of the major nutrients applied to rice. The recovery of N from N applied to wetland rice, however, seldom exceeds 40% (De Datta and Buresh 1989). Thus, new methods or strategies are needed to improve the agronomic and economic efficiency of N fertilizers in rice that would also minimize fertilizer-related environmental pollution. Some of the promising N management techniques include split application, subsurface placement, and the use of slow-release and coated urea fertilizers (Mohanty et al 1999).

We evaluated the relative efficiency of selected controlled-release urea (CRU) and coated urea fertilizers compared with a single basal application of prilled urea on irrigated transplanted rice (cv Ajaya) at the DRR farm, Andhra Pradesh, India. Field trials were conducted during the monsoon (kharif: July to October 1997) and winter

(rabi: November 1997 to March 1998) seasons on a typical Vertisol soil (pH in water 8.3, cation exchange capacity (CEC) 45 cmol P⁺ kg⁻¹, organic carbon 5.5 g kg⁻¹, available KMnO₄-extractable N 150 kg ha⁻¹, Olsen P 30.4 kg ha⁻¹, and NH₄C-extractable K 244.5 kg ha⁻¹). Treatments were four types of fertilizer N and a no-N control (Table 1) arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Types of fertilizer N used were CRU with 4.5% and 6% coating, gypsum-coated urea (GCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), and commonly available prilled urea (PU). CRU, a free-flowing granular fertilizer coated with polyurethane and wax, had 43% N, 1.3% biuret, 120 ppm free ammonia, 0.08% moisture, and 1.8% conditioner. All fertilizers were broadcast in a single dose of 86 kg N ha⁻¹ just before

planting. Phosphorus (P) as single superphosphate and potassium (K) as muriate of potash were applied to all plots at locally recommended rates of 27 kg P and 32 kg K ha⁻¹.

Among different fertilizers, CRU 6% produced the highest grain yields, whereas a single basal application of PU had the lowest yields in both seasons (Table 1). Grain yields obtained with CRU 6% were 38% and 27% higher than those obtained with PU in the monsoon and winter seasons, respectively. In the monsoon season, yield of CRU 6% was significantly higher than that of CRU 4.5%, but, during winter, there was no significant difference in grain yield of the two CRU fertilizers. Grain yields produced by GCU and NCU were similar but significantly lower than those of the two CRUs in the monsoon season. During the winter season, how-

Table 1. Effect of controlled-release and coated urea fertilizers on grain yield and N use efficiency of rice (cv Ajaya) in two seasons, 1997-98, Andhra Pradesh, India.*

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			N uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)			N recovery efficiency (%)			AEN			PFP-N		
	Monsoon crop	Winter crop	Mean	Monsoon crop	Winter crop	Mean	Monsoon crop	Winter crop	Mean	Monsoon crop	Winter crop	Mean	Monsoon crop	Winter crop	Mean
Control	2.3 e	2.1 d	2.2	51.5 e	45.9 d	48.7	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
CRU 4.5%	4.7 c	5.5 a	5.1	101.5 c	84.6 b	93.0	58.1	45.0	51.6	39.6	29.3	34.5	54.2	63.7	59.1
CRU 6.0%	6.0 a	5.7 a	5.9	142.1 a	92.2 a	117.1	105.3	53.8	79.6	42.0	45.2	43.6	70.4	66.2	68.2
GCU	5.4 b	5.2 b	5.3	115.9 b	93.4 a	104.6	74.9	55.2	65.1	35.8	38.2	37.0	63.4	59.9	61.6
NCU	5.2 b	5.1 b	5.1	105.2 c	94.1 a	99.6	58.7	56.0	57.4	34.7	35.4	35.1	60.6	61.2	60.9
Prilled urea	3.7 d	4.1 c	3.9	77.9 d	53.0 c	65.5	30.7	8.2	19.5	23.9	18.3	21.1	43.5	48.0	45.8
CD (5%)	0.35	0.48	—	8.34	5.78	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

*In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at CD 5% probability level. ^bN rate for all sources was 86 kg ha⁻¹. GCU = gypsum-coated urea, NCU = neem oil-coated urea, CRU = controlled-release urea, AEN = additional grain yield over control per kilogram N applied, PFP-N = total grain yield per kilogram N applied, CD = critical difference.

Table 2. Economic analysis of using coated fertilizers.

Treatment	Mean yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Gross value (Rs ha ⁻¹) ^a	Additional labor cost ^b (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net value (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net value to investment (Rs Rs ⁻¹)	Additional value to investment (Rs Rs ⁻¹)	Additional value (%)
CRU 4.5%	5.1	25,400	1,120	24,280	33.1	6.5	24.4
CRU 6.0%	5.9	29,350	1,900	27,450	37.1	10.5	39.5
GCU	5.3	26,500	1,340	25,160	34.0	7.4	27.8
NCU	5.1	25,650	1,170	24,480	33.1	6.5	24.4
PU	3.9	19,500	—	19,500	26.6	—	—

^aUS\$1 = Rs 42.00. Cost of PU = Rs 8.60 kg⁻¹, cost of rough rice = Rs 5.00 kg⁻¹. ^bAdditional labor cost for harvest and postharvest processing of additional produce.

ever, grain yields of CRU 4.5%, GCU, and NCU were on a par and the performance of CRU 6% was significantly superior to that of GCU and NCU.

Agronomic efficiency of applied N (AEN) and partial factor productivity for applied N (PFP-N) (Peng et al 1996) were 43.6 and 68.2 for CRU 6%, respectively. Mean AEN values ranged from 34.5 to 37.0 and the PFP-N ranged from 59.1 to 68.2 for other coated fertilizers. The single basal application of PU was the least efficient (AEN = 21.1, PFP-N = 45.8). Total N uptake was highest in CRU 6% with 117 kg N ha⁻¹ and lowest in the single basal application of PU (55 kg N ha⁻¹).

Financial returns to investment in fertilizers were computed for different fertilizer types. When prices of CRUs and modified urea were assumed to be equal to that of commonly available PU (Rs 8.6 per kg N as PU), the analysis indicated a 24–40% additional net value for money invested in CRUs and modified urea

(Table 2). This means that, if these fertilizers are priced at less than 124–140% of the price of PU, they will be competitive in the market. Mean values over several seasons and sites must be considered to achieve the economic advantage and comparative pricing of CRU fertilizers.

These results revealed that CRU 6% was better than all other coated fertilizers in rice yield, N use efficiency, and plant N uptake. CRU 4.5% was comparable with other coated fertilizers (GCU and NCU). If appropriately priced, CRU fertilizers will be economically competitive with the commonly available PU, and may become an important source of N fertilizer for rice with a high N use efficiency.

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e.ramin@cgiar.org or
t.fairhurst@ppi-ppc.org